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DISTANCE AND HOME LABS – WHAT DO THE SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE SAY?

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ABSTRACT

Labwork is usually seen as an essential element in engineering and science education. One, of the many purposes, with labwork is to strengthen, develop and deepen students' understanding of real phenomena (i.e., objects and events) and the connection between real phenomena and theoretical models and theories. Another main purpose of lab work is to develop students' abilities to collaborate in experiments and empirically investigate and describe technical systems, natural and technical objects, and natural and artificial phenomena.

In connection with distance learning, it is in general a challenge to design labwork in a good way so that the intended learning outcomes mentioned previously are achieved. This does not only apply specifically to the situation with “forced distance teaching” that has arisen in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic, but generally applies to all kinds of “off campus” teaching and learning.

I have carried out a comprehensive exploratory review of what is reported in the science and engineering education research literature regarding laboratory work conducted as distance labs or as home labs. In my paper I will present initial results from my literature review. I have found that there is, indeed, a quite substantial literature describing remote labs and online labs. However, with few exceptions, the literature is mainly focused on the technical aspects of remote labwork and less on the pedagogical aspects. In addition to various forms of “online” labs and remotely controlled labs, I will highlight different forms of home labs and labs with low-cost equipment as an interesting option.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Labs in engineering education

Almost 80 years ago, Müller [1] argued that “there is little evidence to show that the mind of modern man is superior to that of the ancients. His *tools* are incomparably better” (my italics). He reminds us “that the history of physical science is largely the history of instruments and their intelligent use” (ibid.). Indeed, the laboratory is seen as having a “central and distinctive role” in science education [e.g. 2, 3] and as a learning environment that “sets science apart from most ... subjects” [4].

As a result labwork is usually seen as an essential element in engineering and science education. During lab-work, students are expected to *use*, or *learn to use*, symbolic and physical tools (such as concepts, theories, models, representations, inscriptions, mathematics, instruments and devices) in order both to understand the phenomena being studied, and to develop the skills and abilities to use the tools themselves [5]. The aim is that students should develop an understanding of the *relation* between theories and models, and objects and events, and to develop holistic, conceptual knowledge [6]. This is often seen as the fundamental purpose of lab work [7].

The use of laboratory learning activities in formal instruction in science and engineering is intimately related to technology-enhanced learning. In recent decades there has been increasing interest in “technology-enhanced learning”: i.e. the use of new technologies to support the learning in science and engineering. Kyza, et al. [8] have suggested that learning technologies that support meaningful learning in science can be categorized as: a) *scientific visualization tools*, b) *databases*, c) *data collection and analysis tools*, d) *computer-based simulations*, and e) *modelling*.

A common question in the context of technology-enhanced learning and lab instruction is if “computer simulations can replace real experiments”? However, the results from earlier research contrasting similar labs using real versus virtual environments have been contradictory. Some studies have reported better learning results with simulations [9, 10], while other studies have reported that there is a risk that simulations become a world in itself and that students’ do not develop links between theories and models to objects and events in physical reality [11, 12]. However, recent findings indicate that combinations of real labs and virtual labs or real labs and computer-based modelling provide better learning outcomes than either option alone [13-17]. Moreover, engineers need to work with real, complex, systems, non-linear effects, and non-idealized components [18, 19]. Such systems might not easily be modelled using basic laws from science and thus an engineer need to have competence to empirically investigate the behaviour of real systems.

1.2 Labs in distance learning

In connection with distance learning, it is in general a challenge to design labwork in a good way so that the intended learning outcomes mentioned previously are achieved [20-24]. This does not only apply specifically to the situation with “forced distance teaching” that has arisen at many universities world-wide and in connection

with the COVID-19 pandemic, but generally applies to all kinds of “off campus” teaching and learning.

As I am writing this paper we do not yet know how fast and effective the present COVID-19 pandemic can be controlled and stopped world-wide or if some mutations will reduce the effects of (mass-)vaccinations. What we can anticipate is that in some future mankind will experience the outbreak of some, yet unknown, pandemic. Moreover, it is worth noting that not only outbreaks of pandemics and diseases, but also natural catastrophies, fires, and other disturbances can result in a need for rapid change to distance teaching (see, for example, Potgieter et al. [25]). Thus universities need to be prepared. There is also a general interest in society to increase access to higher education through distance education and in this context it is a challenging task to design learning environments that also includes the learning students usually get through labwork and similar practical experiences. In this context the term MOOL (Massive Open Online Lab) have been coined [e.g. 26]).

The demands and challenges mentioned above have lead to the following research question: What is reported in the science and engineering education research literature regarding laboratory work conducted as distance labs or as home labs?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Literature search and review

To answer the research question I searched for articles and book chapters using the Scopus database using search terms such as, for example, “remote lab”, “distance education” AND “lab”, “home experiment”, “‘take home’ lab”. Different synonyms were used and, for example, “experiment” and “practical work” were used as alternatives to the search term “lab”. The title, abstract and keywords of papers were searched and aone limitation was that papers needed to be written in English or German. Another limitation was that the subject area was restricted to subjects typically taught at schools of engineering, i.e. papers related to engineering sciences including material science, physical sciences (physics and chemistry), and environmental and earth sciences. As I were interested in (practical) labwork mathematics were not included and to get a more manageable number of hits pharmacy, medicine, and health and life sciences were not included in the search although I know that there exist interesting publications in these fields. Although online labs can be adapted to learning in a distance mode I deliberately did not include online labs in my search string. One reason for this is that currently the publication of a special issue of European Journal of Engineering Education targeting online labs is in progress and another reason is that I wanted to focus on distance labs, i.e. labs not conducted by students’ while on campus, and thus my search terms would probably catch those papers that describe online labs for the purpose of distance learning. I deliberately did not put any restrictions on year of publication in effect as I wanted to able to find older papers describing at home labs using simple materials as these could still be relevant.

The main body of the search was performed in May to mid July in 2020 with a supplementary search to find recently published papers performed May 2nd, 2021. Hitherto, the search in Scopus has yielded 513 documents (of this total 73 papers were found in the additional search in early May, 2021, i.e. they were indexed in Scopus in the period July 19, 2020, to May 1, 2021).

In the first stage the titles and the abstracts of papers that were found in the search were read. Papers that apparently did not match the research question were excluded at this stage. For example the search term “home lab” also found papers that included the phrase “*smart home lab*” (or similar) in their title or abstract, i.e. (research) labs that were investigating the design and properties of “smart homes” and not labs for education. Although outside the research question, papers focused on school level education (and not higher education) were included in this stage as it could not be a priori be ruled out that such a paper could contain useful ideas.

The papers that remained after this initial screening and could be accessed in full through Linköping University Library were downloaded for a first skim reading of the full texts of the papers to get a first, exploratory, overview of the material. In this (skim) reading it was noted (to the extent information was available in the paper) the topic of the lab, the type of lab, the equipment and technology used, the target audience, the pedagogical design, experiences, and resulting student learning were noted. As this conference paper report a work-in-progress I will in the following not report any quantitative analysis of the material as the analysis is not yet completed. Instead I will as a result of my initial exploratory review in the following section report my general findings and observations from reading the papers. I will also, as examples mention some papers from my literature search.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Types av labs and categorisation

Somewhat simplified, laboratory work can be seen as divided into those that are carried out in the form of a simulation and/or modeling “virtually” and those that are carried out by observing some “real” phenomenon in reality. For the sake of simplicity, I disregard here that it can be successful for the sake of students’ learning in laboratories to combine computer simulations with real measurements (cf. [13-17]). Moreover, students’ access to the resources or equipment essential to carry out a lab can either be local or remote leading to the typical categorisation and types of labs displayed in Table 1 [27, 28].

By equipment and resources is meant the equipment or resources that is critical to carry out a *particular* lab. For example, in a *distributed virtual lab* students typically access a specific, dedicated, webpage through a webbrowser to run a simulation of some specific phenomena. They still need to have local access to a computer, a tablet, or a smartphone to run the simulation (not all simulations will run on any hardware) and they might need a computer or a tablet to write a report. In a *local virtual lab* the simulation or the modelling is can run locally, “off-line”, on students’ (or the lab rooms’) computers (or tablets/smartphones) and access to internet is not

necessary. As more and more resources are placed in the “cloud” I would argue that the distinction between local and distributed virtual labs are becoming more and more blurred. Indeed, both local and distributed virtual labs are commonly referred to as online labs.

Table 1. Types of laboratory experiments (Adapted from [27, 28])

Nature of lab equipment and resources	Students' access to essential equipment or resources	
	<i>Local access</i>	<i>Remote access</i>
<i>Physical (real)</i>	<i>“Hands-on” Lab</i>	<i>Remote Lab</i>
<i>Virtual (simulated / modelled)</i>	<i>(Local) Virtual Lab</i>	<i>(Distributed) Virtual Lab</i>

In a remote lab students control and collect data from an experiment carried out with real, physical, equipment on some remote location (i.e. not in the same room as from where the experiment is controlled). This remote location can be everything from nearby on the same campus to be very far away and even in another country. Typically, but not always, the experiment can also be observed through some camera while running. As with distributed virtual labs students still need a (local) computer to control the experiment, to receive data from the experimental results, and to analyze data. In a “hands-on” lab the experiment is carried out by the students in immediate vicinity and control. It is important to note that nowadays the experiments in “hands-on” labs often are controlled by a local computer and measurements are carried out digitally by sensors or equipment connected to a computer.

One observation from reading the literature is that terms quite often are conflated. I have already mentioned that the term “online” often is used for both local and distributed virtual labs. Another conflation is the use of “virtual” for both virtual labs and remote (real) labs. “Digital” is sometimes used to distinguish virtual labs and remote labs from hands-on labs. However, heavy use of digital tools are common in hands-on labs and the term “digital” is used when one mean distance education or distance meetings.

To avoid confusion when discussing labs in distance education (in the following I also include “distance mode” in this category) I will use the categorisation I have proposed in Table 2. The types of labs in the right column (“remote access”) in Table 1 can easily be interpreted as the types of labs appropriate for distance education. However, as will become evident in the following, I (and the literature) claim that all types of labs in the grey area of Table 2 should be considered for labs in distance education (Traditionally, in distance education, students have also travelled to a university campus for a concentrated, hands-on, lab-course. However, this has for many reasons been cumbersome [20] and in the time of Covid-19 not appropriate).

In the following, I will briefly describe (preliminary) observations from my exploratory literature review.

Table 2. Proposed categorisation of labs for a discussion related to distance education. The labs relevant for distance education is marked by a grey background.

	Students' location			
	<i>On Campus</i>		<i>At home</i>	
Nature of lab equipment and resources	Students' access to essential equipment or resources		Students' access to essential equipment or resources	
	<i>Local access</i>	<i>Remote access</i>	<i>Local access</i>	<i>Remote access</i>
<i>Physical (real)</i>	<i>"Hands-on" Lab</i>	<i>Remote Lab</i>	<i>At home lab</i>	<i>Remote Lab</i>
<i>Virtual (simulated / modelled)</i>	<i>(Local) Virtual Lab</i>	<i>(Distributed) Virtual Lab</i>	<i>At home Virtual Lab</i>	<i>(Distributed) Virtual Lab</i>

A general challenge in distance education, regardless of type of lab, is that students are much on their own in labs and that fruitful collaboration is much more difficult to achieve. Much of the learning gains in successful, on campus, laboratory learning environments have been attributed to students' shared experiences, discussions and collaborative work [5, 29].

3.2 Virtual labs

Virtual simulation and modeling labs can be relatively easily (technically) performed remotely and there is a fairly extensive literature [e.g. 30]. However, there may be requirements for what computer equipment the students have and there may be problems with licenses that do not allow programs to be installed on students' computers or to be run outside the network of the university. This can be circumvented by using students' computers as a remote terminal, but is somewhat cumbersome. A further complication is that all students do not have access to a fast internet connection. In physics in particular, there are ready-made programs and modules that have been developed especially for teaching purposes [31], but even "professional" programs such as Matlab, Simulink or Circuitlab can be used to advantage. As mentioned earlier the literature presents conflicting results regarding students' learning when participating in virtual labs. Above all, it is pointed out that there is a risk that the simulations will become a "world in itself" with little or no connection to reality.

3.3 Remote labs

There is also fairly extensive literature for remote labs [e.g. 32-38]. In addition to descriptions of projects where several universities have merged around remote-controlled multi-user and multi-experiments laboratory work, there is rich literature that describes how remote control can be created with relatively simple equipment

such as Arduino cards. With a few exceptions, however, the focus in the literature is on technical aspects and not on pedagogical issues. The resources (material and personnel) required to build and maintain systems are often not clear. In addition to the pedagogical issues and maintenance of systems mentioned challenges to solve in connection to remotely-controlled labwork are scaling, communication protocols and the lack of standardization.

3.4 At home labs

As a curiosa it can be mentioned that the oldest paper I found in my literature search was one from 1938 in which it was described how a chemistry lab could be built in ones home [39]. However, at home labs are less well described in the literature. At home labs can roughly be divided in three categories: Labs that can be performed with simple materials, labs that utilize the inherent capabilities of modern digital tools such as smartphones and tablets, and labs that utilize low cost digital equipment.

There is a lot of older literature that describes labs that can be performed with simple equipment and with simple materials that are available at home, in everyday life or in the environment [e.g. 40]. There are publications that are aimed at higher education, but mainly the literature is aimed at children and young people of school age or younger. In my opinion, however, this literature is worth studying to get inspiration for suitable experiments that can be adapted to courses at university level through requirements for a different and more advanced analysis of studied phenomena. In addition to the older literature it seems that the forced distance mode have led to the revival of at home labs using, for example, using commonly available materials and resources for physics [41] or turning the kitchen into a chemistry lab [42, 43] or into an electromagnetics lab [44].

The development of increasingly advanced digital tools that at the same time have fallen in price enables home laboratories of a different type than before with more advanced measurements and data processing. Various smartphones such as the iPhone and surfboards such as the iPad contain a built-in camera and built-in sensors that can be used for laboratory work. In my literature study, I have seen that there are constantly examples of new ways to use smartphones and surfboards [45, 46]. In addition to the built-in sensors in smartphones and surfboards, there are sensors and measuring equipment that can be connected to these via Bluetooth. In this way, laboratory work can be carried out that previously required a computer.

The digital evolution has also led to the development of specific measurement equipment that is now available at an affordable price – some technical universities have developed boxes with affordable equipment they allow students to borrow for their own use or buy it [47]. I have already mentioned that Arduino cards have been used to control remote labs. Such cards can also be used for home labs and there is some literature describing this [48]. Other examples are Digilent Analog Discovery which is a small interface (dimensions approximately 8 x 8 x 2 cm) that is connected to a computer's USB input and has the ability to function as an advanced signal generator and a multi-channel oscilloscope with spectrum analyzer among other

features and is therefore suitable for laboratory work in electrical engineering [49]. Another example is iOLab which is a small trolley (3 x 7.5 x 13 cm) that not only has built-in sensors (position, speed, acceleration, force, rotation) that make it suitable for mechanical experiments [50], but it also has sensors for magnetic field, light, sound, temperature, pressure and voltage. Communication with the host computer takes place wirelessly. The literature for Diligent Analog Discovery and iOLab is more limited, but there are already examples of iOLab being used with good learning outcomes (according to concept tests) in distance physics courses [50].

4 SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

In summary, there is fairly extensive literature on remote labs and "virtual" labs that can be used for inspiration. However, the focus is more on technical aspects than on the learning and pedagogical aspects. There is an uneven distribution of subjects with most publications related to teaching in electronics, control theory, mechatronics and physics. For distance labs, I would suggest that it is even more important to think through what purpose and intended learning outcomes you have with a lab and focus the design of the lab on that. Moreover, the literature indicates that the pedagogical design of laboratory work is more important than the technology itself and that the costs of developing good laboratory work and maintaining equipment for remote-controlled laboratory work should not be underestimated.

Personally, I think that labs utilizing low-cost equipment (such as Diligent, iOLab and similar that students can borrow or own) is something we will see of increasing importance and something we will see more of in the future. Such equipment is also of value for campus teaching as it gives students the opportunity to work outside scheduled labs. Such equipment also provides flexibility to meet different developments of the current pandemic and (possible) future pandemics. Finally I note that labs using such type of equipment will enable students to work "by hand and by computer" [cf. 51]. Indeed, it corresponds to the "*postdigital* perspective [in education], in which the digital makes up part of an *integrated totality*" argued by Fawns [52]. I.e. a totality in which digital as well as analogue technologies and tools have its place as well as human senses and embodiment.

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